

SOCIAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF THE INNOVATIVE POTENTIAL OF SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED BUSINESSES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article examines the theoretical and applied aspects of assessing the innovation potential of small and medium-sized businesses in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The relevance of the study is due to the fact that the SME sector plays a significant role in ensuring employment, economic diversification and the development of entrepreneurial initiative, however, its innovative potential is not fully utilized. According to official statistics, as of January 1, 2026, 2,175,600 small and medium-sized businesses operated in Kazakhstan, and the number of employees in the sector amounted to 4,527.4 thousand people, and the output of SMEs in 2025 reached 104,766.3 billion tenge [1]. At the same time, the level of innovative activity of enterprises remains relatively limited and in 2024 was about 11.9% [4]. This indicates that there is a structural gap between the scale of the business sector and its ability to systematically implement technological, organizational, marketing and digital innovations. The article offers a comprehensive approach to assessing the innovative potential of SMEs, including quantitative, technological, financial, personnel, digital and institutional indicators. Based on the analysis of official data and international ratings, the main factors limiting the innovative development of SMEs in Kazakhstan have been identified, and directions for increasing the innovative potential of the business sector have been proposed.

Keywords: *small and medium-sized business, innovation potential, innovation activity, digitalization, entrepreneurship, Kazakhstan, e-commerce, R&D.*

Introduction. In modern conditions, the innovative potential of small and medium-sized businesses is one of the key factors for sustainable economic development, increasing the competitiveness of the national economy and forming a new model of entrepreneurship. Small and medium-sized enterprises have high adaptability, flexibility of organizational structures and the ability to respond more quickly to changes in consumer demand. At the same time, it is this sector that more often faces restrictions in access to finance, technology, qualified personnel, research infrastructure and mechanisms for commercializing innovations.

For the Republic of Kazakhstan, the problem of assessing the innovative potential of SMEs is of particular importance. The small and medium-sized business sector has been demonstrating quantitative growth in recent years, increasing its contribution to employment and output, and gradually expanding its presence in the digital economy. According to the Bureau of National Statistics, as of January 1, 2026, the number of operating SMEs amounted to 2,175,600 units, which is 5.0% more than in the same period of the previous year [1]. The output of SMEs in January–December 2025 amounted to 104,766.3 billion tenge, an increase of 12.3% compared to 2024 [1]. These data show that SMEs are an important sector of the economy, but its innovative component requires a more in-depth analysis.

The relevance of the research is enhanced in the

context of the digital transformation of the economy. The development of e-commerce, marketplaces, fintech services, cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, digital marketing and automated management systems creates new opportunities to enhance the innovative potential of SMEs. In 2025, the volume of retail e-commerce in Kazakhstan, including market places, amounted to 3,768.8 billion tenge, and the share of e-commerce in retail reached 14.3% [2]. This indicates that the digital environment is becoming one of the key channels for the development of entrepreneurship and the formation of innovative business models.

However, a high level of distribution of digital tools does not always mean a high level of innovation potential. Enterprises can use separate digital solutions, such as social networks, online sales, or marketplaces, but they do not have a full-fledged innovation strategy, data management system, process automation mechanisms, and competencies for implementing complex technologies. Therefore, the assessment of the innovative potential of SMEs should take into account not only quantitative indicators of business development, but also its ability to innovate technologically, develop organizationally, and create added value.

The purpose of the article is to assess the innovative potential of small and medium-sized businesses in the Republic of Kazakhstan based on the analysis of official statistical data, international indices and factors of digital transformation.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set:

- to study theoretical approaches to determining the innovative potential of SMEs;
- analyze the current state of small and medium-sized businesses in Kazakhstan;
- to assess the digital, financial, human and institutional factors of the innovative potential of SMEs;
- to identify the main limitations of the innovative development of the business sector;
- to propose ways to increase the innovative potential of SMEs in the digital economy.

Literature review. The concept of innovation potential in the economic literature is considered as a set of resources, competencies, organizational capabilities and institutional conditions that allow an economic entity to develop, implement and commercialize innovations. In the classical sense, innovation is the basis of entrepreneurial development and is associated with the introduction of new combinations of factors of production, new products, markets, technologies and organizational solutions [9].

In relation to small and medium-sized businesses, the innovation potential has a specific character. Unlike large companies, SMEs, as a rule, do not have significant research units, large investment budgets and sustainable access to scientific and technological infrastructure. Therefore, innovations in the SME sector are often implemented through the adaptation of ready-made technologies, the introduction of digital services, business model changes, customer service development, the use of platform solutions and organizational flexibility.

Modern research shows that digital transformation is one of the most important factors in increasing the innovative potential of SMEs. Digital technologies make it possible to reduce transaction costs, accelerate information processing, expand sales markets, personalize customer interaction, and improve the effectiveness of management decisions [10]. However, the introduction of digital technologies requires not only technical resources, but also managerial competencies, organizational culture, the ability to work with data and willingness to change business processes.

In international practice, the innovative potential of SMEs is assessed through several groups of indicators: the level of innovative activity of enterprises, research and development costs, the share of innovative products, the availability of digital infrastructure, access to finance, the quality of human capital, the development of the entrepreneurial environment and the degree of business integration into innovative ecosystems. In this regard, international indexes, including the Global Innovation Index, the E-Government Development Index, and the Network Readiness Index, are an important analytical tool.

According to the Global Innovation Index 2025, Kazakhstan ranks 81st among 139 economies in the world. At the same time, the country's strongest positions are noted in the areas of "Infrastructure" — 64th place, "Human capital and Research" - 68th place, "Institutes" — 77th place. Weaker positions are observed in the areas of "Market development" - 93rd place,

"Knowledge and technological results" — 87th place, "Business development" and "Creative results" - 82nd place [6]. These data allow us to conclude that Kazakhstan has certain basic conditions for innovative development, but faces the challenges of transforming resources into technological and market results.

Materials and research methods. The methodological basis of the article consists of systematic, comparative, statistical and analytical research methods. The systematic approach allowed us to consider the innovative potential of SMEs as a set of interrelated components: resource, technological, financial, human, digital and institutional. The comparative method is used to compare the dynamics of indicators of SMEs, e-commerce and international indices. The statistical method is used to analyze official data from the Bureau of National Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the World Bank, the United Nations, WIPO and other international organizations.

The information base of the study was data from the Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan on the development of small and medium-sized businesses, e-commerce and innovative activity of enterprises; materials from the World Bank on digital infrastructure and the entrepreneurial environment; data from WIPO on the Global Innovation Index; materials from the UN on the E-Government Survey; as well as scientific publications on innovative development and digital transformation of SMEs.

In the framework of the study, the innovative potential of SMEs is considered as an integral characteristic, which includes the following components:

- economic potential, expressed in the number of active SMEs, employment, output and the sector's share in GDP;
- innovation potential, reflecting the level of innovation activity of enterprises, the cost of innovation and the ability to introduce new products and processes;
- digital potential, determined by the level of development of e-commerce, the spread of marketplaces, digital platforms and infrastructure;
- human resource potential related to the number of employees, the level of digital competencies and the ability of staff to adapt to new technologies;
- institutional capacity, including government support, digital public services, innovative infrastructure, technology parks, accelerators, and financing mechanisms;
- market potential, reflecting the ability of SMEs to enter new markets, use digital sales channels and create competitive products.

The following indicators were used to assess the innovation potential: the number of operating SMEs, the number of employees, output, the share of SMEs in GDP, the volume of electronic commerce, the share of electronic commerce in retail trade, the level of innovative activity of enterprises, research and development expenditures as a percentage of GDP, Kazakhstan's position in the Global Innovation Index and E-Government Development Index.

The results of the study. The results of the study

show that small and medium-sized businesses in Kazakhstan have significant economic potential, which forms the basis for subsequent innovative development. As of January 1, 2026, the number of operating SME entities in the country amounted to 2,175,600 units, which is 5.0% more than in the same period of 2025, when this figure was 2,071,700 units [1]. This indicates the continued positive dynamics of entrepreneurial activity and the expansion of the base of potential participants in innovation processes.

The growing number of active SME entities is important for assessing the innovation potential, since it is the number of active business structures that determines the scale of possible implementation of new technologies, digital solutions and business models. However, the quantitative expansion of the sector is not a sufficient condition for innovative development. The innovation potential depends not only on the number of enterprises, but also on their financial stability, technological equipment, managerial culture, digital maturity and risk tolerance.

The number of people employed in the SME sector as of January 1, 2026 amounted to 4,527.4 thousand

people, which is 0.3% higher than the level of the previous year [1]. This indicator reflects the sustainable social importance of SMEs as a source of employment. However, in the context of innovation potential, not only the number of employees is important, but also the quality of human capital. Digital competencies, skills in working with analytical tools, knowledge of electronic platforms, the ability to use CRM systems, digital marketing, cloud technologies and automation tools are of particular importance for the innovative development of SMEs.

The output of SMEs in January–December 2025 amounted to 104,766.3 billion tenge, an increase of 12.3% compared to 2024 [1]. This growth shows that the SME sector not only maintains quantitative stability, but also increases its economic contribution. At the same time, an increase in output can be considered as an important prerequisite for innovative development, since an increase in income and volume of activity creates additional opportunities for investments in technology, digitalization, staff training and modernization of business processes.

Table 1

Key indicators of SME development in Kazakhstan

Indicator	2025 / as of 01.01.2025	2026 / as of 01.01.2026	Change
Existing SME entities, thousand units	2 071,7	2 175,6	+5,0%
Employed in SMEs, thousand people	4 422,1	4 527,4	+0,3%
SME output, billion tenge	81 920,0	104 766,3	+12,3%
The share of SMEs in GDP, January–June 2025	—	39,8%	+1.6 pp.
Note — compiled according to [1], [3].			

The share of SMEs in the gross domestic product is of particular importance. According to official statistics, in January–June 2025, the share of SMEs in Kazakhstan's GDP amounted to 39.8%, an increase of 1.6 percentage points compared to the corresponding period of the previous year [3]. This indicates a gradual strengthening of the role of the business sector in the national economy. At the same time, for the transition to an innovative development model, it is necessary that the contribution of SMEs to GDP is formed not only through trade and traditional services, but also through technologically more complex activities, digital services, industrial innovations, creative economics and export-oriented business models.

An analysis of the structure of innovation potential shows that digitalization is one of the most dynamic areas of SME development. In 2025, the volume of retail e-commerce in Kazakhstan, including marketplaces,

amounted to 3,768.8 billion tenge. For comparison, in 2021, this figure was 482.0 billion tenge [2]. Consequently, in 2021-2025, the volume of retail e-commerce increased almost 7.8 times. This indicates a significant expansion of the digital market space in which SMEs can sell goods and services without the need for significant investments in the traditional trading infrastructure.

The share of e-commerce in total retail trade is also showing growth. In 2021, it was 3.6%, in 2022 — 12.5%, in 2023 — 12.7%, in 2024 — 14.1%, and in 2025 it reached 14.3% [2]. Despite the slowdown in the share of e-commerce after 2022, the volume of the digital market itself continues to increase. This means that e-commerce is becoming a sustainable channel for the development of entrepreneurship, and digital platforms are an important factor in the innovative potential of SMEs.

Table 2

Dynamics of e-commerce in Kazakhstan

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
The volume of retail electronic commerce, billion tenge	482,0	1 963,5	2 439,8	3 156,4	3 768,8
The share of e-commerce in retail trade, %	3,6	12,5	12,7	14,1	14,3
Volume of e-commerce services, billion tenge	349,9	1 186,5	1 602,6	2 443,4	2 477,3
Note — compiled according to [2].					

The development of marketplaces has a significant impact on the innovative potential of SMEs. In 2025, marketplaces accounted for 3,237.5 billion tenge, or 86% of the volume of retail electronic commerce, while enterprises' own Internet resources accounted for 531.3

billion tenge, or 14% [2]. This structure shows that marketplaces have become the main digital channel for businesses. This has a dual meaning for SMEs. On the one hand, marketplaces reduce barriers to entry, provide access to a wide audience, payment infrastructure,

logistics services, and promotion tools. On the other hand, high dependence on form boards may limit entrepreneurs' independence in managing customer data, pricing policy, brand, and communication channels.

In this regard, the digital potential of SMEs should be assessed not only by their presence on marketplaces, but also by the level of independent management of digital assets. Those enterprises that combine the use of marketplaces with the development of their own online stores, CRM systems, customer bases, sales analytics, digital marketing and loyalty systems have a higher level of innovation potential. This combination allows businesses not only to sell through platforms, but also to create their own digital business model.

Despite the positive dynamics of digitalization, the innovative activity of enterprises in Kazakhstan remains limited. According to official statistics, in 2024, the level of innovation activity of enterprises was about 11.9% [4]. This means that only a small part of enterprises systematically implement new products, technologies, processes or organizational solutions. This indicator is one of the key constraints on the innovation potential of SMEs, as it demonstrates the gap between the scale of the business sector and the real intensity of innovation processes.

A comparison of indicators of SME development and innovation activity allows us to identify a contradiction. On the one hand, the SME sector in Kazakhstan is showing growth in terms of the number of operating entities, employment, output and share in GDP. On the other hand, the level of innovation activity remains significantly lower than the economic scale of the sector. This means that a significant part of entrepreneurship develops mainly on the basis of traditional business models, while the potential for technological renewal, digitalization of production processes, introduction of new products and commercialization of innovations is underutilized.

An additional factor characterizing the innovation potential is the level of research and development costs. According to WIPO, Kazakhstan's gross expenditures on R&D in 2023 amounted to about 0.14% of GDP, an increase of 0.03 percentage points compared to the previous year [6]. Despite the positive dynamics, this indicator remains low compared to developed innovative economies. Limited spending on research and development reduces the possibility of creating new technologies, scientific and technical solutions, and commercializing research results in the business sector.

Table 3

Indicators of innovation and digital potential of Kazakhstan

Indicator	The value	The year	Interpretation for SMEs
Innovative activity of enterprises	of about 11.9%	is 2024	Low proportion of enterprises implementing innovations
Spending on R&D, % of GDP	is about 0.14%	2023	Limited scientific and technological base
Kazakhstan's place in the Global Innovation Index	81 out of 139	2025	Average level of innovative competitiveness
Place for infrastructure in GII	64	2025	Relatively strong infrastructure base
A place in Human capital and research at GII	68	2025	Availability of a base for innovation development
Place in terms of market development in GII	93	2025	Limitations of the market environment for innovation
Place in knowledge and technological results in GII	87	2025	Insufficient transformation of resources into innovative results
Note — compiled according to [4], [6].			

Kazakhstan's positions in the Global Innovation Index 2025 confirm the existence of a mixed picture of innovation potential. The strengths are infrastructure, human capital and institutions, which creates the basis for innovative development. However, weaker positions in terms of market development, knowledge and technological results show that the available resources are not effectively transformed into innovative products, technologies, patents, exports of high-tech services and new business models [6].

An important element of the innovative potential of SMEs is the digital public infrastructure. Kazakhstan ranks 24th among 193 countries in the UN e-Government Development Index for 2024, with an EGDI of 0.9009 [7]. This is a significant advantage, since advanced digital government services reduce administrative barriers, simplify business registration, obtaining solutions, interaction with government agencies, and access to electronic services. For SMEs, this creates the

institutional conditions for faster start-up and scaling of business activities.

However, a high level of e-government does not guarantee the automatic growth of the private sector's innovation potential. State digitalization must be complemented by the digital maturity of the enterprises themselves. If a business uses digital government services but does not implement internal automation, data analytics, digital sales, and modern management systems, the overall innovation effect remains limited. Therefore, an important task is the transition from the digitalization of public services to the digital transformation of business processes.

Access to digital infrastructure in the regions is essential for the innovative potential of SMEs. In 2024, the World Bank approved the financing of the Kazakhstan Digital Acceleration for an Inclusive Economy project in the amount of 92.43 million US dollars, aimed at expanding broadband access in underserved

regions of the country [8]. It is expected that the implementation of such projects will contribute to reducing digital inequality and expanding opportunities for SME development in rural and remote areas. This is especially important for innovative entrepreneurship, because without high-quality Internet, it is impossible to fully use e-commerce, cloud services, digital payments and online learning.

The analysis of the factors of innovation potential allows us to identify several key limitations. The first limitation is related to the financial accessibility of innovations. Most SMEs do not have sufficient own funds to implement new technologies, automate processes, purchase software, and train staff. Traditional bank loans are often focused on less risky projects, whereas innovative activities are characterized by uncertain results and a longer payback period.

The second limitation is related to human resources. The innovative development of SMEs requires specialists with competencies in digital marketing, data analytics, project management, e-commerce, financial planning, cybersecurity, and business process automation. However, many small enterprises are unable to attract highly qualified specialists on an ongoing basis, which reduces their ability to innovate technologically.

The third limitation is the weak integration of SMEs with scientific, educational and innovation infrastructure. Universities, scientific organizations, technoparks and acceleration programs operate in Kazakhstan, but the interaction between small businesses and the scientific community remains insufficiently systematic. This limits the commercialization of research and reduces the likelihood of technological startups based on scientific developments.

The fourth limitation is related to the industrial structure of SMEs. A significant part of small and medium-sized businesses are concentrated in trade and services, where innovations are often organizational, marketing or digital in nature, but not always related to technological production. This does not reduce the importance of such innovations, however, it limits the possibilities of forming a high-tech entrepreneurial sector.

The fifth limitation is related to regional heterogeneity. In large cities such as Almaty and Astana, entrepreneurs have greater access to digital services, human resources, financial institutions, educational programs, and sales markets. In regions, especially in rural areas, the innovative potential of SMEs is often limited by infrastructural, human and logistical factors.

Table 4

Comprehensive assessment of the innovative potential of SMEs in Kazakhstan

The innovation potential component	Current status	The main problem	The direction of development
Economic potential	Growth in the number of subjects, employment and output	Quantitative growth is not always accompanied by innovation	The transition from extensive growth to technological renewal
Digital potential	Rapid growth of e-commerce and marketplaces	Dependence on external platforms	Development of SMEs' own digital channels
Financial potential	Availability of support programs	Limited access to innovative financing	Grants, digital vouchers, guarantees, venture instruments
Human resources potential	Employment growth in SMEs	Lack of digital competencies	Training of entrepreneurs and employees
Scientific and technological potential	Availability of scientific base and infrastructure	Low R&D costs and weak commercialization	The relationship between science, business and government
Institutional capacity	Advanced e-government	Insufficient transformation of state digitalization into business innovation	Supporting the digital maturity of enterprises
Market potential	The growth of digital markets	Limited export and technological orientation	Support for entering new markets
Note — compiled by the author based on [1]–[8].			

Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the innovative potential of SMEs in Kazakhstan is at the stage of formation and is characterized by a combination of strengths and weaknesses. Strengths include the scale of the sector, increased output, a high proportion of operating enterprises, the development of e-commerce, the availability of digital government infrastructure and the gradual expansion of digital markets. Weaknesses include low innovation activity of enterprises, limited spending on R&D, a shortage of digital competencies, weak commercialization of scientific results, dependence on marketplaces and regional heterogeneity.

For a more accurate assessment of the innovative potential of SMEs, it is advisable to use an integrated approach based on a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators. This approach should include not only statistical indicators, but also an assessment of the digital maturity of enterprises, their willingness to innovate, the level of managerial competencies, the availability of financing, and the degree of involvement in innovative ecosystems.

The proposed system for assessing the innovative potential of SMEs can include five levels. The first level is basic, when an enterprise uses minimal digital

tools and does not have an innovation strategy. The second level is adaptive, when businesses apply individual digital solutions, such as online sales or social media. The third level is functional, when the company implements CRM, electronic accounting, digital marketing and platform sales. The fourth level is integrated when

digital technologies are associated with financial management, logistics, customer base and data analytics. The fifth level is innovation, when an enterprise uses artificial intelligence, automation, its own digital products, R&D and new business models.

Table 5

Levels of innovation potential of SMEs

Level	Characteristic	Typical tools	Capacity assessment
Basic	Lack of systemic digitalization	Messengers, simple online communication	Low
Adaptive	Using separate digital channels	Social networks, marketplaces	Below average
Functional	Digitalization of individual business processes	CRM, online sales registers, e-commerce	Average
Integrated	Linking digital solutions to management	ERP, analytics, logistics automation	Above average
Innovative	Creating new products and business models	AI, Big Data, R&D, Digital platforms	Tall

The practical significance of the proposed assessment lies in the fact that it makes it possible to differentiate measures of state and institutional support. Basic-level enterprises need, first of all, training and access to simple digital services. Enterprises at the adaptive level need support for the transition from marketplaces to their own digital channels. Functional-level enterprises need process automation and access to finance. Integrated-level enterprises can be export-oriented, technologically advanced, and participate in acceleration programs. Innovative enterprises should receive support in technology commercialization, intellectual property protection, and entry into international markets.

Thus, the results of the study show that the innovative potential of SMEs in Kazakhstan cannot be assessed solely through the number of enterprises or the volume of output. It is a complex system in which the economic scale must be complemented by digital maturity, access to finance, human resources, scientific and technological base and the ability to create new products. It is the combination of these factors that determines the real ability of small and medium-sized businesses to act as a driver of innovative economic development.

Discussion. The results obtained indicate that Kazakhstan's small and medium-sized businesses have a significant economic base for innovative development, but this potential is not yet fully realized. The growth in the number of operating SMEs, the increase in output and the expansion of e-commerce create favorable conditions for technological renewal. However, the low level of innovative activity of enterprises and limited spending on research and development show that the business sector is still more focused on operational development than on the systematic introduction of innovations.

The contradiction between the high level of digitalization of certain sectors of the economy and the insufficient innovative maturity of business deserves special attention. Kazakhstan holds high positions in the field of e-government, which indicates a well-devel-

oped digital public infrastructure. However, the digitalization of public administration should be complemented by the digitalization of business processes within enterprises. Otherwise, digital transformation will remain primarily an administrative rather than an entrepreneurial development factor.

The development of e-commerce is one of the most positive signs of the growth of the innovative potential of SMEs. The rapid growth of e-commerce shows that entrepreneurs are actively using digital sales channels. However, the dominance of marketplaces simultaneously creates risks of platform dependence. Therefore, the next stage of development should be the strengthening of SMEs' own digital assets: online stores, CRM systems, customer databases, digital marketing and data analytics.

An important area for increasing innovation potential is to expand access to innovation financing. For many SMEs, innovative projects remain risky and expensive. In this regard, government support should be focused not only on traditional lending, but also on grants, digital vouchers, guarantees, venture financing, acceleration programs and support for technology startups.

Equally important is the development of human capital. The innovative potential of an enterprise is determined not only by the availability of technology, but also by the ability of employees and managers to use these technologies to improve business efficiency. Therefore, SME support programs should include training in digital communications, innovation management, data management, e-commerce, financial planning, and project management.

Conclusion. The conducted research allows us to conclude that the innovative potential of small and medium-sized businesses in the Republic of Kazakhstan has a significant economic basis, but requires further qualitative development. The SME sector is showing steady growth: as of January 1, 2026, 2,175,600 SMEs operated in the country, the number of employees amounted to 4,527.4 thousand people, and output in 2025 reached 104,766.3 billion tenge [1]. The share of SMEs in GDP in January–June 2025 was 39.8%, which

confirms its importance for the national economy [3].

At the same time, the innovative activity of enterprises remains insufficiently high and amounts to about 11.9% [4]. This indicates the need to move from quantitative expansion of the business sector to qualitative development based on digitalization, technological renewal, competence development and integration into innovative ecosystems.

Digital transformation creates new opportunities to enhance the innovative potential of SMEs. The growth of e-commerce to KZT 3,768.8 billion in 2025 and an increase in its share in retail trade to 14.3% show that digital markets are becoming an important area of entrepreneurial development [2]. However, for sustainable growth, it is necessary to reduce the dependence of SMEs on marketplaces and develop their own digital channels, customer management systems, data analytics and business process automation.

The scientific novelty of the article lies in the proposal of an integrated approach to assessing the innovative potential of SMEs, including economic, digital, financial, personnel, scientific and technological, institutional and market components. The practical significance of the study lies in the possibility of using the proposed assessment system in the development of programs to support small and medium-sized businesses, digitalization of entrepreneurship and the development of regional innovation ecosystems.

To increase the innovative potential of SMEs in Kazakhstan, it is advisable to implement the following measures: to introduce diagnostics of the digital maturity of enterprises; to expand access to innovative financing; to develop digital competencies of entrepreneurs; to strengthen business ties with universities and scientific organizations; to support SMEs' own digital channels; to develop regional innovation centers; to stimulate technology commercialization and the entry of innovative enterprises into foreign markets.

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